

Themes, Streams, and Lenses in Knowledge Transfer Research

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Abstract—Knowledge transfer (KT) is a well-established research field that can be examined through various themes, streams, and lenses. This bibliometric study aims to identify the fundamental components of these three areas in KT research by analyzing 103 papers from the Web of Science (WoS) using a combined conceptual and intellectual structure analysis in Biblioshiny. Four central themes were identified: performance & management, innovation, absorptive capacity (AC), and capabilities. The co-occurrence network analysis revealed strong connections between these themes, with the strongest link between management and innovation. Four theoretical streams were identified: paradox stream, capability stream, AC stream, and IT stream. The first three streams are rooted in organizational learning theory, and the IT stream is based on knowledge management (KM) theory. The historiographic analysis uncovered four lenses commonly employed in KT research: agent-based, mechanism-based, relational-based, and routine-based lenses. These lenses provide different perspectives for analyzing KT processes at various organizational levels. However, this bibliometric study highlights that KT is strongly linked to organizational learning theory and can be viewed as a process that is analyzable within identified themes, streams, and lenses. It contributes to the KT field by facilitating the alignment of knowledge across diverse themes, streams, and lenses, thus enabling a more profound understanding of the KT domain.

Keywords—Bibliometric analysis, knowledge management, knowledge transfer, lenses, streams, themes.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE is broad scholarly consensus regarding the development of KT research: it is well-established and commonly conceptualized as a process by which knowledge is transmitted from one agent [1] or unit [2] to another, with the intent that the receiving party is able to utilize the received knowledge [1].

However, KT literature exhibits considerable diversity in terms of central thematic areas, theoretical streams, and theoretical lenses [1]. This heterogeneity complicates the research process and makes systematic engagement with the field more difficult.

Accordingly, it is of interest to KT scholarship to provide an integrative overview of the central thematic areas (themes) and theoretical streams (streams) that structure the field, as well as the theoretical lenses (lenses) through which they are typically explored.

Central thematic areas denote dominant research themes (e.g., management) that aggregate various sub-themes. A theoretical stream refers to a set of foundational assumptions that guide research within a given theory (e.g., the learning

curve stream in organizational learning theory) [3]. In contrast, a theoretical lens provides a more specific analytical angle or perspective through which a researcher approaches and interprets a given theoretical stream (e.g., a cognitive lens in the learning curve stream) [4]. Therefore, this bibliometric study pursues the aim of offering an overview of themes, streams, and lenses within the field to provide an advanced understanding of the KT domain.

The following three research questions guide this study:

- RQ1. Which themes play a central role in KT research?
- RQ2. Which streams structure KT literature?
- RQ3. Which lenses are most commonly employed in KT research?

II. METHODOLOGY

A bibliometric analysis was conducted to address the research questions, focusing on the conceptual and intellectual structure of the KT field. The conceptual structure analysis involves identifying key concepts, and the intellectual structure analysis involves identifying influencing structures in the existing knowledge structure [5]. WoS was chosen as the primary data source, and the literature was refined to include only articles published in the Journal of Knowledge Management from 2009 to 2025. This approach was selected to ensure a high level of data quality, facilitated by the standardized format of this journal, and to maintain a strong degree of consistency in the KM data.

After data cleaning was performed using OpenRefine, a Java-based data cleaning tool, two duplicate entries were removed [6].

The resulting dataset, which comprised 103 publications, was subsequently analyzed using Biblioshiny in Bibliometrix, an R-based tool for bibliometric analysis. To address RQ1, a co-occurrence network analysis was conducted. For RQ2, a co-citation network analysis was applied, while RQ3 was explored through a historiographic analysis [7].

III. FINDINGS

This section outlines the key findings of this study.

1. RQ1: Themes in KT Research

The aim of a co-occurrence network analysis is to examine the conceptual structure and discover themes (keywords) in a research field that together form occurrences, that is, connections. The size of the nodes indicates the frequency of

that heterogeneity among organizational learners can be beneficial, as it supports a hybrid strategy that simultaneously leverages both exploration and exploitation.

Uzzi [10] emphasizes the benefits and risks of embeddedness in strategic alliances and networks. Embeddedness can facilitate problem-solving “on the fly” and promote learning through a culture of feedback, thereby enhancing knowledge recombination and responsiveness. However, he also warns of the paradox of over-embeddedness: when firms become too reliant on network ties, their adaptability may decline. This is because of increasing resource dependency, which may lead to the erosion of competitive advantage if key actors exit the network, institutional forces reshape the market, or the network becomes structurally rigid.

Levinthal and March [11] address the paradox “myopia of learning,” which they categorize into temporal, spatial, and failure-related forms. To mitigate this, they propose two mechanisms: (1) simplification to reduce the complexity of experience-based KT and (2) specialization by structural differentiation, where learning is deliberately constrained in one part of the organization and promoted in another. This facilitates specialization in learning capabilities and reduces adjustment pressure in subunits that are less exposed to environmental change.

b) Capability Stream in Organizational Learning Theory

Grant [12] conceptualizes tacit knowledge as “knowing how,” in contrast to explicit knowledge, which he describes as theoretical or factual. The distinction lies in their transferability and the mechanisms required for their transfer across individuals, space, and time. He argues that explicit knowledge functions as an information good and is relatively easy to transmit. By contrast, the value of tacit knowledge lies in its application, which demands a higher transformation effort. Drawing on the work of Kogut and Zander [13], Grant [12] posits that the transfer of tacit knowledge between individuals is especially difficult, being slow, costly, and uncertain, particularly when the knowledge cannot be codified, must be acquired through practice, or cannot be directly observed in its application. He defines KT as a two-stage process involving transmission and reception and introduces a capability view, suggesting that the recipient (individual or organization) must possess a certain AC to integrate new knowledge with existing knowledge structures. Grant [12] further introduces the notion of aggregation capability, meaning that knowledge must be transferable and combinable in such a way that it can be appropriately redistributed in the form of decision-making authority. He also stresses the need for appropriability, which allows for economic returns from knowledge assets, and specialization, which supports efficient knowledge production, understood as a combination of knowledge creation, acquisition, and storage. He contrasts this with organizational learning theory and a knowledge-based view, which focus more heavily on knowledge acquisition and creation. Grant [12] suggests that knowledge creation should be viewed as an individual activity, while the organization's primary role is to coordinate specialized knowledge production efforts. Under the

assumption that tacit knowledge creation dominates, he argues that KT is not an efficient mechanism for knowledge integration. Instead, organizations should strive for effective knowledge integration and minimize KT through mechanisms such as cross-learning. Grant [12] identifies specific integration mechanisms, including rules, directives, sequential processes, routines, group-based problem-solving, and decision-making. He views the outcome of knowledge integration from a capability perspective in which competitive advantage is achieved through organizational integration mechanisms.

Teece et al. [14] argue that the traditional resource-based view (RBV) needs to be expanded to explain how competitive advantages are sustained under conditions of high uncertainty and change (i.e., the VUCA world). While the RBV historically emphasized the accumulation and protection of assets, Teece et al. [14] introduce the concept of dynamic capabilities—defined as the organization's ability to renew and reconfigure competencies in response to changing environments. These capabilities are tied to the strategic management domain, enabling firms to adapt effectively to turbulence.

Kogut and Zander [13] focus on the concept of combinative capabilities, highlighting that competitive advantage arises from the organization's capability to combine existing knowledge with new knowledge. Such combinations often lead to innovation, particularly in domains that involve technological knowledge.

c) AC Stream in Organizational Learning Theory

Cohen and Levinthal [15] introduced the concept of AC, defining it as a firm's capability to recognize the value of new external knowledge, assimilate it, and apply it for commercial purposes. They highlight factors that influence AC development, such as the existence of in-house R&D activities and technical training programs for employees. Central to their argument is that prior knowledge is a prerequisite for effective assimilation, as it enables individuals and organizations to learn more efficiently. Both authors also emphasize the interdependence between individual and organizational AC, noting that efforts to enhance AC at the organizational level must include initiatives to build the AC of individual members. In this context, KT within and between organizational units becomes crucial. This is particularly evident through individuals operating in boundary-spanning roles to facilitate the translation of complex technical knowledge across organizational and external interfaces. However, the authors emphasize that boundary spanners alone are not enough; domain-specific expertise among recipients is also required for proper assimilation. Thus, the use of a shared language is crucial. Moreover, overly homogeneous organizational environments may hinder knowledge assimilation due to the Not-Invented-Here (NIH) syndrome. Cohen and Levinthal further argue that AC is particularly important when the firm seeks to acquire knowledge that is distant from its current knowledge base, thereby requiring active capability development.

Zahra and George [16] build upon this foundation by introducing the ACAP model, conceptualizing AC as a dynamic

establish a historical reference, represented by the direction of the arrows. This indicates that a study strongly refers to a study that was conducted in the past [21]. This correlation is particularly evident in the green cluster. Three research papers from 2018 to 2023 refer to a source dating back to 2014 [22]. In this context, the local citation score (LCS) plays a role because it indicates the frequency with which a source was cited within this cluster [21]. As shown in the example with the green cluster, the source was cited five times, which indicates a high LCS in the green cluster. In contrast, a score of one or two is more of an indication that fewer works refer to the source. The global citation score (GCS), which is reported in WoS, can reaffirm the relevance of a work for the entire field of research [21]. For example, the reference above has a GCS of 52, which is a good score. Although the work of Kumar and Ganesh scores 2.46 times higher (GCS = 128). In this study, the LCS is considered in conjunction with the sources to identify the lens through which the investigations have been conducted. Four clusters were identified, indicating the presence of the four lenses.

a) Agent-Based Lens

The first lens is made up of the works of Kumar and Ganesh [1] and Krylova et al. [23]. The historical reference is to Kumar and Ganesh [1] (LCS = 4).

In their study, Kumar and Ganesh [1] present a morphology based on eight dimensions: study, knowledge, agents, flow, mechanisms, contextual factors, geography, and business context. This morphology is intended to promote an understanding of the KT field. In their study, they lens KT from an agent perspective. An agent represents an actor involved in KT, which corresponds to a source that has knowledge and a recipient that requests knowledge. In such a way, it can also be viewed in terms of different organizational structures at the organizational, team, and individual levels.

In their study, Krylova et al. [23] describe that improvisation processes of knowledge workers can have a positive effect on KT. The authors define improvisation as an ability that can be promoted by managers. According to the authors, this shifts the focus from explicit KM tools and strategies to a process view, which should serve as a micro-basis for KT and knowledge protection. They refer to knowledge translation theory and argue that knowledge must be translated in order for an understanding to emerge on the receiving end and that improvisation can support this translation process. This is demonstrated using an example of a training situation. Training can be viewed as an episodic event in which KT is an ongoing process: an employee who tries out knowledge in professional practice can achieve a higher chance of benefiting from KT and close the gap between the knowledge transferred and the professional reality because he translates the transferred knowledge for himself through improvisation. Moreover, knowledge can be translated into a network. According to Latour's actor-network theory (ANT) [24], non-human agents can also be used in addition to human agents. Krylova et al. [23] define KT like Kumar and Ganesh [1] from the agent-based lens.

b) Mechanism-Based Lens

The second lens identified in the historiographic map comprises two studies: Joia and Lemos [25] and Casprini et al. [26]. There is a historical reference to Joia and Lemos here [25] (LCS = 3).

Joia and Lemos [25] examine the dynamics of tacit KT (TKT) within a single organization based in Brazil. Their work draws on Polanyi's [26] foundational definition of tacit knowledge, which he describes as the capability to solve problems based on experiential insight embedded in the knowledge holder. They position TKT within a personalization strategy framework, as articulated by Hansen et al. [27], focusing on the role of social exchange in facilitating KT. The authors identify several factors that positively influence TKT within organizations: interpersonal openness, training programs such as mentoring and coaching, and incentive systems. Both authors further highlight that face-to-face interactions are more effective than formal information systems in supporting the transmission of tacit knowledge.

Turning to Casprini et al. [28], the focus shifts toward barriers to KT. Qualitative data from interviews show that in family-owned businesses, the absence of formal TKT mechanisms becomes problematic as the firm grows. The lack of structured communication channels hinders knowledge sharing regarding activities and competencies. In inter-organizational contexts, they argue that knowledge incompatibility can act as a significant barrier to effective TKT. Nevertheless, they also identify enablers of TKT, including shared narratives, delegation mechanisms, and the presence of a trust-based network.

c) Relational-Based Lens

The third lens is based on the work of Delgado-Verde et al. [29] and Cruz-González et al. [22]. The historical reference here is to Delgado-Verde et al. [29] (LCS = 4).

Delgado-Verde et al. [29] take a relational-based view of radical innovation, stating that in Spanish high- and medium-high-tech organizations, relational-based intellectual capital can have an impact on the ability to innovate. They emphasize that relational-based knowledge can be built up primarily through informal relationships between employees. However, the authors point out that this can lead to "myopia of learning" [11] because organizations then only look inward in their search for new knowledge and ignore the outside world. Organizations should therefore reduce their reservations about taking external knowledge and should span their boundaries.

In their study, Cruz-González et al. [22] attempt to create an understanding of how much time Spanish high-tech organizations should invest in the search for external knowledge. They show that openness to external knowledge is not always an advantage. On the one hand, it can be an advantage for innovation performance from a relational-based view, but it can also turn out to be a disadvantage, namely, if costs and dependence on the supplier (e.g., providers of market knowledge) increase as a result of excessive absorption and spillover effects.

d) Routine-Based Lens

In the fourth lens cluster, there are three contributions with the same LCS of 2. Here, there is only the historical reference of Xi et al. [32], once to Koch [30] (LCS = 2), and once to Wang et al. [31] (LCS = 2).

Koch [30] investigates the implementation of KT routines at the level of product development (PD) teams. Her study focuses on KT between two PD teams, conceptualized as autonomous agents, and places particular emphasis on the characteristics of the transferred knowledge, especially its tacit nature. Here, TKT emerges as a complex process that requires embedded routines and context-specific coordination mechanisms at the intra-organizational team level.

Wang et al. [31], on the other hand, examine KT routines in the context of cross-border mergers and acquisitions (M&A). In this inter-organizational setting, this study identifies knowledge compatibility as a key determinant of successful KT. Drawing on congruence theory, they postulate that routine compatibility, defined as the alignment and synchronization of operational routines, is a critical facet in facilitating knowledge integration during M&A processes.

Xi et al. [32] consider knowledge integration from a routine-based view to investigate the relationship between unlearning and KT. By a routine-based view, the authors mean the view that routines can contribute to stability, for example, by normalizing processes. However, they also refer to the view that routines can also become outdated and useless, referring to the study by Wang et al. [31]. The study also refers to Koch [30] in that organizational routines are linked to the capability to integrate knowledge and can be characterized as mechanisms.

Fig. 3 Historiographic map in KT research (generated with Biblioshiny)

IV. DISCUSSION

This chapter aims to answer the three research questions and emphasize the limitations of this work. Table I summarizes the key findings of this bibliometric study.

1. RQ1: Which Themes Play a Central Role in KT Research?

A total of four central thematic areas were identified: performance & management, innovation, AC, and capabilities. This bibliometric study shows that management and performance as key themes are particularly well developed.

The link to innovation can be recognized particularly well in the literature on the streams (RQ2). Strategic management must make efforts to strengthen a company's performance and competitiveness. The ability to innovate refers to organizational learning and thus learning to influence internal processes to achieve an increase in performance. Analyzing capabilities helps to examine the prerequisites for absorbing external knowledge. This also creates a link to AC, especially with the exploration efforts of an organization in the process of KT.

2. RQ2: Which Streams Structure KT Literature?

The initial stream is anchored in the realm of organizational learning theory and is primarily focused on the paradoxes inherent in this field. As a result, it can be referred to as "paradox stream" within the context of organizational learning theory.

The second stream, therefore, embodies organizational learning theory within the central thematic cluster of innovation and capabilities, as it explores both the prerequisites and dynamic capacities necessary for KT and innovation. Consequently, it can be classified as a "capability stream" in organizational learning theory.

The third stream is rooted in organizational learning theory and can be mapped onto the central thematic field of AC, with conceptual linkages to knowledge acquisition, dynamic capabilities, and sustained competitive advantage. Although Barney [17] did not explicitly address AC in his study, he argues that for an organization to compete sustainably, it requires resources that significantly differentiate it from the competition. The AC theory offers a processual explanation of how such knowledge as strategic resources can be integrated and exploited for competitive advantage. In summary, the contributions under consideration herein focus on an AC stream, and thus it can be referred to as "AC stream" in the context of organizational learning theory.

The fourth stream is situated within the theory of KM, focusing on the enabling conditions and systemic capabilities required for effective KM processes. The subject discussed attaches particular importance to the field of information technology; therefore, it is referred to as "IT stream" in the context of KM theory.

3. RQ3: Which Lenses Are Most Commonly Employed in KT Research?

The first lens can be classified as an "agent-based lens," as it employs an agent perspective on the management for approaching KT and how this process takes place in general and can be supported.

The second lens can be situated within the broader organizational learning stream as it enables the analysis of learning mechanisms across organizational boundaries and structures. Therefore, it represents a "mechanism-based lens,"

offering analytical leverage for investigating how and under what conditions knowledge can be transferred within and between organizations.

The third lens represents a “relational-based lens,” focusing on the relational conditions that prevent, distort, or delay the effective transfer of external knowledge. This also raises questions concerning the AC of the receiving units and the appropriateness of the transfer mechanisms under varying structural constraints.

The fourth lens, the “routine-based lens,” enables researchers to view KT mechanisms as organizational routines at varying structure levels—whether between teams within an organization or across different organizations. This perspective allows for an exploration of where KT processes are embedded in the organizational architecture.

TABLE I
THEMES, STREAMS, AND LENSES IN KT RESEARCH

Themes	Streams	Lenses
performance & management	paradox stream in organizational learning theory	agent-based lens
innovation	capability stream in organizational learning theory	mechanism-based lens
AC	AC stream in organizational learning theory	relational-based lens
capabilities	IT stream in KM theory	routine-based lens

4. Practical Implications

From a methodological perspective, these findings show that the bibliometric techniques used in this study can be employed in future research to examine the conceptual and intellectual structure of a research field such as KT. Moreover, researchers can use Table I as a guide to develop their own research design. For example, researchers could consider contributing to the IT stream. To do so, they could approach the theme of capabilities from a mechanism-based lens and derive the research question of which mechanisms can help a particular organization transfer technological knowledge. For organizations themselves, these findings mean that they can address the topic of KT from various perspectives to assess their knowledge production and make appropriate changes. It is advisable to start with an agent-based lens, examine the flows of knowledge, evaluate the relationships and routines, and subsequently consider which mechanisms could be introduced to innovate their knowledge production.

5. Limitations

This study has several limitations. Firstly, the methodological scope was confined to a single database, WoS, and included only articles published in one journal, specifically the Journal of Knowledge Management. Future research should consider broadening the analysis to encompass additional publication sources and bibliographic databases to enhance coverage and representativeness. Secondly, the bibliometric analysis was restricted to examining conceptual and intellectual structures. A social structure analysis, such as through co-authorship or institutional collaboration networks, was not conducted. Incorporating such an analysis in future studies could offer more in-depth insights into the relational

dimensions of the research landscape, including the identification of scholarly communities, influential author clusters, and patterns of academic collaboration.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to identify themes, streams, and lenses within the KT field. To achieve this, a bibliometric analysis was conducted, focusing specifically on the conceptual and intellectual structure of the field. The analysis uncovered four themes, streams, and lenses, highlighting the strong foundation of KT in organizational learning theory. Additionally, the literature perceives KT as a process that is analyzable through a paradox stream, a capability stream, an AC stream, and an IT stream. The research further indicates that KT can be examined from various lenses, including a mechanism-based lens, a routine-based lens, a relational-based lens, and an agent-based lens. In summary, the KT field is connected to the question of which competence framework should be established for effective KT. In this context, it may be beneficial for researchers to concentrate on a specific theme, stream, and view KT through one of the identified lenses. By fostering an understanding within the KT field, this study significantly contributes to the field of KT by facilitating the alignment of knowledge across diverse themes, streams, and lenses.

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